

Problems of tribal girl child

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ABSTRACT

At the time of birth of a girl child, it is necessary for the family members to understand her major needs and requirements. At the time of birth of the girl child, it is necessary for the family members to understand her major needs and requirements. The main needs are care, affection and warmth. From an early age parents need to create awareness about adequate diet and nutrition, health care, dress, play items and all other childhood activities. When girls start growing up, they need to enroll in nursery schools so that the foundation for learning can be built effectively. On completion of nursery schooling, they enroll in formal schools, where they receive elementary, secondary and senior secondary education. Upon completion of formal schooling, admission to higher education institutions is considered optional. But in the present existence, the importance of education has been accepted to a great extent that it has become mandatory not only for men but also for women to pursue higher education. Girl child is considered as the future not only in India but also in other countries. But the circumstances are not the same for every society. When we look at the tribal society, we find that social evils are prevalent in the tribes, which have a harmful effect on the lives of the girl child. Girls have freedom in tribal society but in some cases they have to face social restrictions. In tribal rural communities, girls are considered a liability and preference is given to male children. In other words, people do not appreciate the birth of girls. Whereas, in urban communities, well-educated and wealthy individuals treat girls as equals and provide them with the same rights and opportunities as boys. In this research paper, an attempt has been made to understand the problems of tribal girls of Puso Panchayat of Sisai block of Gumla district of Jharkhand. Due to problems like child labor, child marriage, malnutrition, exploitation, child trafficking, neglect and social discrimination, child mortality and child abuse, tribal girls are not able to develop and they lag behind in improving their future generation. For the development of tribal society, it becomes even more necessary to understand the problems of girls.

Keywords: girls' problems, tribal girl child, Jharkhand Gumla,

INTRODUCTION

Looking at the past of the development of human civilization, it is known that human problems have emerged in the course of development itself. With the development of civilization human had to face several of problems. Globally, no matter how developed a country is, its problems are multiplex in proportion to its development. Whatever may be the society, it has to face some or the other major issues. There are many complications in the issues of the developing nation as

compared to the developed nations. In these dilemmas the problems of tribal girl child are also connected.

India is developing fast, particularly in the field of Medicine, Architecture, Technology, Space Exploration. From a bird's eye see – yes, the progress is exalted. However, when you search deeper and carefully, you soon realise that we still lack in many crucial aspects. The status of the girl children in the country is one of the issues which certainly need to be focused on. On one hand, we have Saina Nehwal, PV Sindhu, Sania Mirza and Mary Kom breaking all the dividing line and proving their worth, while on the other hand, many innocent daughters do not even make it into this world. One side of India considers women as ideal, and the other side considers them inoperable. Are we really concern on the other side of India? Here are some challenges faced by daughters in the country time and again. Unfortunately, these issues are still maligning the figure of developing India.

In every society, girls have to face many problems. But when it comes to tribal society, the problems of girl children are even more complex. is full of struggle and difficulties. The effect of poverty, illiteracy, geographical environment is clearly visible in their lives. The life of tribal girls is also full of struggle and difficulties. It is said that tribal women are independent and strong. But the other aspect is that many responsibilities are put on the shoulders of girls from a young age, they are unable to live their childhood to the fullest. Its effect is seen in the future and development of girls.

Now it is necessary to know, who is this child? According to international law, a person below the age of 18 years is considered a child. This definition has been accepted worldwide. This definition is found in the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. This convention is an international law on which most of the countries have given their consent. Individuals below the age of 18 are treated as a separate legal entity in India. This is the reason why we can neither vote nor enter into any legal contract before the age of 18 years. Under the Child Marriage Restraint Act, 2006, the marriage of a girl below the age of 18 years and a boy below the age of 21 years has been declared illegal. The definition of UNCRC should also be included in such laws. After ratifying the UNCRC in 1992, the Government of India has amended its juvenile justice laws to provide for state care and protection for every child under the age of 18 who is in need of such assistance.⁹

Review of literature

Singh Ayushi has written in his article that “According to the Jharkhand Economic Survey conducted in 2015-16, the enrolment of girl students at primary and upper primary levels was found to be 50%. Moreover, female literacy in urban areas was 77.5 per cent in comparison to about 55.2 per cent in rural areas. Further, Jharkhand has the highest dropout rate for school children in India (only 30 out of 100 finish school). Dropout rates among Adivasis are the

highest among all communities. ” Poddar Sanjay Kumar in an article titled ‘Problem of tribal girl child labour of Jharkhand’ has told about the causes of tribal girls of Jharkhand becoming child labour and the harm caused to the girl child. He writes that their parents and guardians are also unable to educate in place of meaning, importance is given. The girl child will go to another home, so Lee does not see the need to spend on her education.

Objective of the study

The object of study is the core or method of any scientific research. The development of any society is judged by the condition of the women of that society. The status of a woman lies on how her life has passed from childhood to youth. Since women are equal part of the society and girl child is the initial stage of life. Therefore, the main objective of doing this research was to understand the problems of tribal girls closely and try to search their solutions so that it would help in connecting the tribal society to the path of development.

Methodology

Purposive sampling method was used. Tribal families of four villages Puso, Nijma, Kulkupi and Garwali of Puso Panchayat were selected and collected as informants. Direct interviews were conducted with the informants. Daily activities of girls aged 6 to 18 years were observed. Group interviews were conducted on problems related to women and girls.

Finding of the study

Study Area

Jharkhand ("The land of forest") is a state in eastern India, created on 15 November 2000, from what was previously the southern half of Bihar. The tribes of Jharkhand consist of 32 tribes inhabiting the Jharkhand state in India. The Scheduled Tribe (ST) population of Jharkhand State is as per 2001 census 7,087,068 constituting 26.3 per cent of the total population (26,945,829) of the State. The Scheduled Tribes are primarily rural as 91.7per cent of them reside in villages. District wise distribution of ST population shows that Gumla district has the highest proportion of STs (68.4per cent).⁵The most popular one ascribes to its word ‘Gumla’ in Mundari language, which relates to the occupation of the local Tribes in rice processing work (dhan-kutna).As per 2011 census, 93.65 % population of Gumla districts lives in rural areas of villages. Since obvious that the district has a total of 68% of tribal population, therefore, it comes within scheduled area .³Sisai block is situated at the east of Gumla. Main occupation is agriculture and fishing. They also make forest produce goods likeTokri, Sup. etc.⁴

The present study has been conducted among tribal families living in four villages Puso, Nijma, Kulkupi and Garwali of Puso Panchayat of Sisai block of Gumla district. In these villages, the maximum number of Oraon tribe and Munda, Lohra, Mahali and Chikbadai tribes live. This is a

tribal dominated area. The village is away from the cities amidst plateaus and jungle-bushes. There are private schools as well as government schools in the villages. Pucca roads, electricity has reached the villages. The primary data has been collected on the basis of micro field study. Its analysis has been presented in detail. The information has been presented in both quantitative and qualitative form.

TABLE 1

The data of families obtained from four villages of Pus0 Panchayat is shown below.

Name of village	No. of family	MALE	FEMALE
PUSO	12	37	46
NIJMA	13	40	62
KULKUPI	13	39	42
GARWALI	12	35	53
TOTAL	50	151	203

According to Table-1, the total number of males in 50 families is 151 and the number of females is 203. In which the number of males in the four villages Pus0, Nijma, Kulkupi and Garhwali are 37, 40, 39 and 35 respectively. and females are 46, 62, 42 and 40 respectively. It is known from this table that the number of females is more than that of males.

TABLE 2

Classification of women by age

AGE	0-5 YEAR		6-12 YEAR		13-18 YEAR		OVER 19 YEAR	
NUMBERS	46	22.66%	43	21.18%	32	15.76%	82	40.39%
TOTAL	203							

According to Table-2, the number of girls of 0-5 years is 46(22.66%), 6-12 years 43(21.18%), 13-18 years 32(15.76%) and girls above 19 years are 82(40.39%).

TABLE 3

Educational details of 6-18 years old girls and over 19 year women

6-18 years old girl (in 75)		Over 19 years women (in 82)	
literate	illiterate	literate	illiterate
67	89.33%	41	50%
8	10.67%	41	50%

As per Table-3, out of total 75 girls in the age group of 6 to 18 years, 67(89.33%) girls are literate and 8(10.67%) girls are illiterate, they don't even have alphabet knowledge. Out of total 82 females in the age group above 19 years, 41(50%) females are literate and 41(50%) females are illiterate. Data was collected from age group of 6 to 18 years by answering yes or no to the questions related to their problems as shown below.

TABLE 4

PROBLEM FACED BY TRIBAL GIRLS CHILDREN

PROBLEMS OF GIRL CHILDREN	YES		NO	
	No. of answering	%	No. of answering	%
Gender inequality (in 75)	56	74.66	19	25.34
Domestic violence (in 75)	41	54.66	34	45.34
Child labour (in 75)	59	78.66	16	21.34
Child marriage (13-18 years girls)	9	28.12	23	71.88
Education (in 75)	67	89.33	8	10.67

It is known from the above table that 56 girls feel that they face gender inequality. Parents fulfill their demands less than sons. He is allowed to go out even less than his daughter. Girls are asked to do more work than boys. On domestic violence, 41 girls have accepted that apart from their parents, they have also faced beating, abusing and mental harassment by other family members. On child labour, 59 girls admitted that they have to work in other houses, shops and fields for money. It also includes girls aged 14 to 18 who have ever worked before the age of 14. On child marriage, 9 out of 32 girls in the age group of 13 to 18 years admitted that they faced pressure from parents or elders in the household to get married. The reason for this is Dukku marriage by the adolescent boys and girls of the society. In such a situation, the girl chooses a young man according to her wish and starts living in his house without getting married according

to traditional customs. In this way, the tradition of living together without getting married is called Dukku marriage, but the couple who do Dukku marriage does not get any kind of social recognition. Parents see such incidents around them and get the girls married early. All this affects the education of girls. The table shows that out of 75, 67 girls are literate and 8 girls are illiterate. Out of that 46 girls admitted that they face problems in studies. They don't go to school every day. Girls have to do household and farm work daily. Wood has to be brought from forests and mountains for fuel. One has to work even during farming. Due to this, their interest in studies remains low. Their parents also do not give priority to studies due to poverty.

CONCLUSION

From the above description, we can conclude that the population of girls is good, so they do not have to face the problem of female foeticide. Also, it is known from table 2 that their number is also increasing. If we look at education, there is improvement as per table 3. that is, parents send their daughters to school. Table 4 depicts the problems of girl children. The biggest problem is in the education of girls. Girls also have to do labour. Girls also have to face domestic violence. Girls are also pressured by their parents to get married. According to the 2015-16 Jharkhand Economic Survey, most of the students leave the school midway. Only 30 out of 100 girls complete school. Most of them come from tribal society. From this research I come to the conclusion that girls do not go to school but also do not withdraw from school. Everything looks better on the surface but poverty and backwardness have brought many problems before the tribal society. Instead of reducing their problems, they remain the same. Therefore it becomes necessary to understand and solve the tribal problems.

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